

THE ROLE OF CULTURE AND ART IN STRENGTHENING THE VALUES OF YOUTH OF NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article highlights the role of culture and art in strengthening the values of the youth of New Uzbekistan. It also provides an analysis of the work done by the Ministry of Culture to promote the national and universal values of young people.

Keywords: youth, New Uzbekistan, values, culture, art, national, universal, upbringing, spirituality

Admirable paintings are being achieved in our country to completely recognize the abilities and competencies of young people, to completely recognize their noble aspirations, to increase their social activity, and to occupy a worthy location in lifestyles. At the start of those works, all of us see that the Honorable President himself is an example. Educating younger humans within side the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland, and respect for countrywide and prevalent values, extensively regarding the developing younger technology in technology and innovation, main them to "New Uzbekistan - Towards the Third Renaissance!" measures geared toward unification across the slogan are being evolved and placed into practice. In each of the decrees and selections followed within side the area of lifestyle and artwork, measures associated with the difficulty of youngsters had evolved. For example, with inside the selection of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 28, 2018 "On approval of the idea of in addition improvement of countrywide lifestyle in Uzbekistan" No. PQ-4038, May 26, 2020, Decree No. 6000 [1:211, 423], February 2, 2022 "On measures to boom its position and have an effect on within side the lifestyles of society" Addendum at the, in addition, improvement of the sector of lifestyle and artwork on measures" No. PQ-112 [2:1] and the selection of the Cabinet of Ministers on April 6, 2018 "Recognizing artists who've made a notable contribution to the improvement of our countrywide lifestyle and Uzbek artwork On March 20, 2019, "On measures to guide younger humans who've been effectively appearing on their stages", "Performers of Folk Instruments", "Performers of National Dance" named after Mukarrama Turgunboyeva, and

Yunus Decision No. 237 "On the protecting of republican examinations for younger reputation executors" named after Rajabi. a, on August 26, 2019, with inside the selection No. 718 "On in addition improvement of the gadget of significant employer of unfastened time of younger humans in Andijan place through regarding them in lifestyle and artwork institutions", dated August 21, 2019, November within side the selection No. 923 "On the, in addition, in addition, improvement of the gadget of significant employer of unfastened time of younger humans with inside the Republic of Karakalpak Stan, areas and the metropolis of Tashkent through regarding them in lifestyle and artwork institutions" [3:470-477] and No. 685 of November 16, 2021 "On measures to arrange and preserve the republican competition of younger performers "Shashmaqom" with inside the Bukhara place" [4: www.lex.uz] evolved the above-noted measures plans evolved. The Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan has evolved separate roadmaps for the difficulty of youngsters and is sporting powerful paintings on this basis. Educating younger humans with inside the spirit of countrywide and prevalent values is a concern in all of the works completed with inside the area of lifestyle and artwork. Figure 1 underneath suggests the information on the record of sports completed through the Ministry of Culture in 2019-2020 to draw younger humans to lifestyle and artwork.

We talk a lot about strengthening the values of young people, but the question arises, what is the value itself? How is it defined? So, values are a concept used to show the importance of existence, society, things, events, human life, and material and spiritual wealth... Value can be historical and modern. There are different forms of value: material, spiritual, universal, regional, universal; economic, social, political, and cultural value in the spheres of society's life; moral, religious, legal, and scientific, corresponding to forms of social consciousness; national, class, party values, etc., which correspond to the social structure of life. [6:323,324] We are witnessing the incomparable role of culture and art in the formation and strengthening of spiritual, universal, material, cultural and social forms of values in young people in today's intensive reforms. State theaters, theater studios under the system of the Ministry of Culture, the Uzbek National Status Art Center, the Republican Arts Center, the State Dance Ensemble "Bahor" named after M. Turgunboyeva, the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan (Fergana and Nukus branch), State Conservatory of Uzbekistan (Nukus branch), State Academy of Choreography of Uzbekistan

(Urganch branch), Uzbek National Music Art Institute named after Yunus Rajabi, Botir Zakirov.

National Institute of Pop Art, Republican Specialized Pop and Circus College named after K. Zaripov, Republican College of Music and Art, Republican Specialized Music School named after R. Glyer, Republican Specialized Music School named after V. Uspensky, cultural centers, children's music and art Institutions such as horse schools, boarding schools specialized in culture and art have been doing a great service to educate young people in the embodiment of national and universal values through the field of culture and art. One of the main tasks of the leaders of regions, ministries, and agencies is to create the necessary conditions for young people who show their talent in the fields of culture, art, science, and education. [7:259]

The formation of good ideas and strengthening of values in the youth of new Uzbekistan depends on the correct implementation of the principles of peace and democracy in this country.

No matter how much democracy and political culture acquire a universal meaning and value, its basis, which gives it spiritual strength, enriches it and ensures its diversity, are national-spiritual values. [8:20 a.m.]

We can say that studying the heritage of our ancestors will be a great motivation in raising the young people of new Uzbekistan to be educated, spiritual, and loyal to national and universal values. Because the legacy of our ancestors is a great gift for us young people.

The great legacy of our ancestors, which began with the honor of independence and is now being studied as a great spiritual need, is now being enriched with a new image. This is the spiritual world of national independence. If we are committed to this work, are working to renew the spiritual image of our nation, and are striving to understand our national values, let us, first of all, use the heritage of our great martyrs more effectively. Only then will we fulfill our filial duty to their memory. Only then will we feel the feelings of human perfection, spiritual peace, and high faith. [9:22]

In the years of independence, centuries-old efforts were made to cultivate the feeling of love for the Motherland and the nation in the hearts of the young generation. The immortalization of the memories of the commanders like Sahibqiron Amir Timur, and Jalaluddin Manguberdi, who fought for the freedom of the country, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulhamid Cholpon, and their comrades, who became a symbol of devotion to the country and the nation, and the high respect for the symbols of our country - the flag, the coat of arms,

and the national anti anthem formations clear evidence of this. That's why today the words "We will not give you to anyone, Uzbekistan!", "This dear Motherland belongs to all of us" are not just slogans, they are becoming a call to the heart, a political belief, a and value of the nation's youth. [10:51]

Nowadays, certain categories of people have stopped thinking about anything other than the market. The parent is in the market, the child is in the market. What do we expect tomorrow from the children selling water on their heads in the bazaar, selling spirits or tobacco? Is it possible to send the children who chased the money market all day back to school to live in the conditions of market laws?. Recently, that is, on February 2, 2022, with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-112 "On additional measures to further develop the sphere of culture and art", the 2022-2023 academic year performance of tunes on at least one of the national musical ins instruments or improve the musical knowledge and skills of pupils and students in educational institutions, to form a love for national culture in their hearts, to identify and support young talents learning skills are taught and a note about this is made in their educational document (certificate). In addition, there is one study hour per week for music, as well as weekly practical circles and optional lessons on playing tunes on national musical instruments.

The national values, customs, and traditions of our people have been created for thousands of years, and they have become the lifestyle and daily needs of people. He preserved his language and national beliefs from generation to generation. [12:3]

In Uzbekistan, which is developing and modernizing in every way, life itself shows that, along with the economy, high culture, and national spirituality are necessary for young people who have reached the heights of advanced science. In this sense, it is the first task of all of us to mobilize all our efforts to educate our youth, who are the creators of the future of our country, to be patriotic, loyal, and highly spiritual.

We need to create all the necessary conditions so that our young people, whose blood flows from our great grandfathers, can become worthy heirs of our great ancestors, strive for great goals and achieve great goals. We will use all the possibilities so that the youth of New Uzbekistan can rise to such high levels. [13:263]. Therefore, it is necessary for the youth of New Uzbekistan to make good use of the conditions created and to always respond to the service for the glory of our country.

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